

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

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STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

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Citation: Seeber, M., Vlegels, J., & Seeber, M. (2022). Exploring the impact of COST Actions on scientific collaboration. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti2239). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6906731>

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26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Exploring the impact of COST Actions on scientific collaboration

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Abstract: Scientific networks are highly interconnected, but also display traits that are not optimal for the flow and creation of knowledge, such high clustering, homophily and fragmentation. A mechanism that typically affects the possibility to collaborate is proximity. Proximity is especially important to establish collaboration, whereas scientists are then able to continue a collaboration also despite a large distance. From this perspective, it is important to analyse the effects of the Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) research funding framework of the European Union. COST was established in 1971 to connect (mostly) European national scientific systems through transnational research networks called “Actions”, which encompass a range of networking tools, including meetings, conferences, short-term scientific missions, and training schools. The goal of this study is to explore whether participation in a COST Action impacts on the level of scientific collaboration and production between active members of an Action, namely on scientific co-publications. The results show a remarkable average increase of co-publications between active members (+55% compared to non-funded Actions), and an increased involvement of scientists from peripheral countries (i.e., inclusive target countries). The impact of COST Actions persists after their conclusion, and the increase of collaborative co-publications does not come at the expense of non-collaborative ones, meaning a net increase of the scientific production.

Introduction

Collaboration plays a pivotal and growing role in modern Science. Scientific communities are highly interconnected and constitute a “small world,” with just five or six steps necessary to get from one randomly chosen scientist in a community to another, which is a desirable crucial feature of a functional scientific community (Newman, 2001).

The mechanisms and forces which determine how teams of collaborative scientists are assembled importantly affect their creativity and success (Guimera et al. 2005). The probability and capability to establish any social tie is also affected by so-called proximity and assortativity mechanisms (Rivera, Soderstrom, & Uzzi, 2010). As a result, scientific networks are not only highly connected, but also highly clustered (Newman, 2001).

As a result of such mechanisms, Scientific networks may not necessarily display optimal properties for the creation of new knowledge. They may display undesirably high levels of closure, homophily and fragmentation, hindering the integration of scientists with different perspectives, from peripheral countries and institutions, and in turn reducing the potential for the generation of new knowledge (e.g., Powell et al. 2005; Weatherall and O'Connor 2020). To address such issues and promote collaboration, dedicated resources and investments may be necessary. With this rationale, support schemes for research that allow scientists to meet for some time and on a regular basis may enable new and durable collaborations, overcoming some of the structural constraints that too often limit collaboration across physical, social, institutional, and disciplinary boundaries.

From this perspective, it is interesting to analyse the effects of the Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) research funding framework of the European Union. COST was established in 1971 to connect (mostly) European national scientific systems through transnational research networks called “Actions”. A COST Action encompasses a range of networking tools, including meetings, conferences, short-term scientific missions, and training schools. A prime objective of COST Actions is to provide structural support to European Research Area, by promoting cooperation in science and technology between scientists located in the 32 member countries and beyond, which work in academia, public and private research centres and industry, by bridging participation gaps in Europe and including small communities in geographically dispersed regions.

Accordingly, the goal of this study is to explore whether participation in a COST Action has a visible impact on the level of scientific collaboration and production between active members of an Action, namely on scientific co-publications, and whether such effect persists after the conclusion of the Action. Empirically, we explore whether the number of articles resulting from a collaboration between active members of a Cost Action increases during and after the Action, when compared to i) articles not resulting from a COST-related collaboration and ii) articles resulting from a collaboration between proposers of Actions that were non-funded.

By looking at co-publication data, this study also investigates the effect of actively participating in a COST Action in terms of the capability to integrate in the scientific network members from inclusive target countries (ITC).

Data and Methods

Data

The COST

The COST framework was established in 1971, it is the oldest pan-European framework for funding in science and technology. The goal of COST is to connect (mostly) European national scientific systems through transnational research networks called “Actions”, which can also involve non-academic partners. A COST Action encompasses a range of networking tools, such as meetings, conferences, short-term scientific missions, training schools, publications, and dissemination activities. Funding covers all networking tools, with an average support of €520,000 per project and a duration of four years. COST Actions are open to all members from academia, public institutions, industry, NGO, European/international organizations, from different career stages, from 39 COST Members—although non-COST members from so-called near-neighbour countries and international partner countries can also join based on mutual benefit. Proposals should be led by a Chair and should include applicants from at least

seven COST countries. In a proposal an unlimited number of researchers from each country can join, and two per country are nominated to join the Action Management Committee as a Delegate. Currently, the funded actions involve 30 COST Member countries on average.

COST Dataset

We will rely on data from COST regarding the funded actions and a sample of non-funded actions as a control group. We used information from two datasets.

A dataset including information on the proposals and applicants:

-Proposals: identifying code, title, keywords, summary-abstract of maximum 200 words, date of submission, starting date, ending date, status (funded or not), research areas of expertise.

-Applicants: name, surname, gender, year of birth, nationality, country of residence, city of residence, year of PhD degree (null if no PhD degree), institutional affiliation, type of institution, research areas of expertise, level of expertise in each area, role in the action (chair, delegate, suppleant), how many times each member joined the Action activities (meetings, short-term missions, training schools).

An auxiliary dataset with the hierarchical disciplinary classification employed by COST, including 750 research areas and their respective subfields (out of 40) and fields (out of six). Fields and subfields are derived from the Revised Field of Science and Technology (FOS) classification of the Frascati Manual 2002, whereas the lower level (research areas) is specific to COST. The classification has remained the same throughout the five calls.

Publication data

Scientific collaboration is often operationalized as co-authorship on peer-reviewed publications (Sonnenwald 2007). To examine the impact of participating in a COST Action we took into consideration the scientific production both before and after the start of the Action through Scopus database. One challenge was represented by the disambiguation of the authors. Using data from the COST dataset about the name, surname, city of residence and affiliation, we were able to identify and collect data for 22,844 out of 27,210 members of the funded Actions (84.0%), and for 17,673 of the 20,854 active members (84.7%). The share of identified participants is similar across Actions (mean 83.6%, standard deviation 6.2%, max 97.9% and min 60.7%) and countries (mean 84.2%, standard deviation 7.2%).

Method

Descriptive analysis

The first part of the empirical analysis explores the impact of the COST Actions on scientific collaboration through graphs that visualize, for every year from five year before the start of the action to seven years after: i) the publications co-authored by the members of an Action, i.e., collaborative publications, and ii) the publications from members that were single authors or in collaboration with non-members, i.e. non collaborative publications. Both are presented in reference to their value at the starting year of a project; in other words, they are normalized by value in year 0, so that in year 0 they have a value 1. We focus specifically on active members, namely members that have participated at least once to one of the networking activities of the Action, i.e., i) meetings, ii) short term scientific mobility (STSM) and iii) training schools.

Separate analyses are developed to highlight the impact on i) collaborative papers from active members in general, ii) collaborations with and between ITC members.

Furthermore, to estimate the impact on collaborative and non-collaborative co-publications of a COST Action, we study the evolution over time in the number of collaborative co-publications and the non-collaborative publications by i) active members of funded actions, ii) non-active members of funded actions and iii) members of non-funded proposals. This allows us to explore whether Actions have a substitution effect - meaning that an increase in collaborative co-publications is associated with less non-collaborative publications, or an additional effect.

Inferential analysis

We run regression models to explore whether active participation in a COST action affects a member's number of collaborative co-publications, controlling for other traits of the member and the Action, as well as exploring which specific traits of a member and of an Action predict a greater increase in co-publication.

We consider the period that runs from five years before the start of the Action until seven years after. The dependent variable is the yearly number of a member's co-publications with another member of the action. The variable is over dispersed (i.e., the variance increases faster than the mean). For similar dependent variables, negative binomial regressions are preferred to Poisson regressions because they include a distinct parameter to model overdispersion (Snijders and Bosker, 2012).

The data have a three-level structure, with years nested into action-members, nested within Actions. We employ a multilevel regression model, which disentangle the variance due to individual and contextual factors and more accurately computes estimates (Robinson, 2009; Snijders and Bosker, 2012).

Empirical analysis

Descriptive Analysis

Impact on scientific collaboration

Figure 1 represents the evolution over time of scientific co-publications among active participants. It presents for each year, from five years before the start of the Action to 7 years after, the: A) Number of publications of cost Action members with at least two active members as co-authors, normalized by the value at $t=0$ vs. B) Number of publications with only one active - member as co-author normalized by the value at $t=0$ (no collaboration).

The number of collaborative co-publications represents 20% of the total publications in our sample (127.357 out of 611.518), and 53% of the publications after the start of the Action (67.597 out of 127.357).

Figure 1 shows that - compared to their value at year 0 - both collaborative and non-collaborative publications have been growing in the five years preceding the start of the Action and remain rather stable for the two following years. However, the number of non-collaborative publications also remain stable afterward, whereas collaborative publications grow between year three and five and stabilize afterwards. In other words, participation with a COST Action

is associated with a growth of co-publications between active members, which in year 5 can be quantified as 14% higher compared to non-collaborative publications. It is important to notice that the effect does not disappear after the end of the Action, which therefore has a remarkable and persistent effect on collaborative co-publications.

Figure 1 - Evolution over time in collaborative publications between active members vs. non-collaborative publications¹

Figure 2 explores the publication trend for non-active members.

Figure 2 - Evolution over time in collaborative publications of non-active members vs. non-collaborative publications

¹ Note: the boxplot ranges from the first to the third quartile; the vertical line incorporates most observations, more specifically everything within 3 times the interquartile distance from the median, and excluding outliers; the horizontal line in the boxplot identifies the mean

Figure 3 illustrates similar data for members of non-funded proposals.

Figure 3 - Non funded proposals: evolution over time in collaborative publications between proponents of the Action vs. non-collaborative publications.

Integrate in the scientific network members from Inclusive Target Countries

Figure 4 represents the evolution over time of scientific co-publications from the COST Actions, comparing the: A) Number of publications of cost Action members with at least two active members as co-authors of which at least one is from ITC - normalized by the value at $t=0$ vs. B) Number of publications with only one active member as co-author, normalized by the value at $t=0$ (no collaboration).

Figure 4 shows participation with a COST Action is associated with a growth of co-publications of ITC active members, which in year 5 can be quantified around 14% compared to non-collaborative publications - which is stronger than the general effect on collaborative publications.

Figure 4 - Evolution over time in collaborative publications with at least two active members as co-authors of which at least one is from ITC vs. non-collaborative publications

Impact on scientific production

Table 1 shows the median Action's variation over time in collaborative and non-collaborative publications of: i) active members of funded Actions, ii) non active members of funded Actions and iii) members of non-funded Actions. It reveals that the growth in collaborative publications for active members does not happen at the expense of non-collaborative publications.

Table 1 - Median variation in collaborative and non-collaborative publications for active and not active members of funded actions and members of non-funded proposal

publication year from start Action >		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
collaborative publications	active	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	9,8%	10,5%	15,8%	16,7%	13,6%
	non-active	0,0%	0,0%	-10,6%	-11,8%	-12,5%	0,0%	-25,0%	-33,3%
	not funded*	0,0%	0	-1,8%	-8,7%	-15,8%	-16,7%	n.a.	n.a.
non-collaborative publications	active	0,0%	0,0%	2,2%	3,9%	4,1%	6,6%	1,6%	0,0%
	non-active	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	-2,7%	0,0%	-6,1%
	not funded*	0,0%	0,5%	-0,3%	2,3%	1,8%	0,9%	n.a.	n.a.

*Actions submitted in 2015

Inferential Analysis

Figure 5 presents the 95% confidence interval around the coefficients resulting from two regression models. Model 1 explores the main effect of the predicting variables, whereas Model 2 also includes the interaction effects with the variable "Cost Action".

Figure 5 - Coefficients with 95% confidence intervals of two negative binomial regressions predicting the yearly number of collaborative publications of each member

Model 2 reveals that active members display a stronger tendency to collaborate with other members before the start of the Action, which becomes even stronger - in absolute terms, and compared to the non-active members, during the Action and after the Action. Members from ITC collaborate more with other Action members than non-ITC members. This difference may be due to a selection effect, namely, that scientists from a peripheral system are likely to be involved only when already strongly embedded in the network. The interaction between ITC member status and Cost Action, reveals a positive small effect during the Action and a non-significant effect after the action. Male scientists have a stronger propensity to collaborate with other members of the Action. At the same time, during and after the Action, female scientists' propensity to collaborate increased more, which suggests that Cost Actions successfully increased women participation in the network of collaboration.

Conclusions

The goal of this study was to explore the effects of participating in a Cost Action on the level of scientific collaboration. The results show on average a remarkable increase of co-publications between an Action's active members, including interdisciplinary publications, and an increased involvement of scientists from peripheral countries (i.e., inclusive target countries), early career researchers, and women. The impact of active participation in an Action is not limited to the period of the project, but it persists also after its conclusion. The increase in collaborative publications does not come at the expense of non-collaborative publications, which points out to a net positive effect on the scientific production.

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